

What Citizens Search and Municipal Websites Offer

Helena Häußler^a

^a Hamburg University of Applied Sciences, Finkenau 35, Hamburg, 22083, Germany

1. Purpose and Background

Governments around the world are working to expand digital access to public services. In Europe, the Single Digital Gateway Regulation requires member states to provide centralized access to administrative services via portals like “Your Europe.”² Similarly, in Germany, the Online Access Act (OZG) aims to make services available online through unified platforms, such as “Servicesuche Bund.”³ These initiatives promise user-friendly access to administrative information—but uptake remains limited.

The eGovernment Monitor highlights this usage gap: 56% of respondents registered their vehicles offline, and among them, nearly 40% either did not know the online service existed or could not find it (Initiative D21 & Technische Universität München, 2024). Prior research (Hertzum, 2022) suggests that e-government use strongly depends on situational factors, such as ease of finding relevant information and prior user experience.

While earlier studies (e.g., Jansen & Spink, 2007; Lambert, 2013) analyzed user search behavior, they are often outdated or focused on non-European contexts. Serrano-Cinca and Muñoz-Soro (2019) showed a promising match between user searches and content on Spanish municipal websites, but key topics like employment and tourism were still underrepresented.

To date, no similar study has examined whether German municipal websites provide the information users actually search for—a question that is equally relevant for other countries seeking to build effective, user-centered e-government services.

2. Design / Methodology / Approach

Building on the approach by Serrano-Cinca and Muñoz-Soro (2019), this study examines how well German municipal websites align with user search behavior. The following research question is posed: *Do municipal websites in Germany provide the information users are searching for?* The central assumption: search engines remain a primary gateway to digital public services.

Using 98 keywords related to administrative tasks, transparency, and public participation—including priority services under the German Online Access Act (e.g., marriage registration, driver’s license issuance)—this study evaluates the Google ranking of municipal websites. The Result Assessment Tool (RAT) was used to collect search volume and identify the top ten results for each keyword in April 2025.

The analysis includes four cities in Northern Germany—Hamburg, Lübeck, Ahrensburg, and Dagebüll—representing various administrative levels and population sizes.

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EMAIL: helena.haeussler@haw-hamburg.de

ORCID: 0000-0001-7420-571X

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² URL: <https://europa.eu/youreurope/index.htm>

³ URL: <https://servicesuche.bund.de/#/de/>

3. Expected Findings

Search topics like jobs, local events, or leisure are likely to generate more searches than administrative processes. However, municipal websites face stronger competition from commercial platforms for popular topics. In contrast, for core government tasks like regulations or social services, municipal websites may rank higher due to their content authority.

It is also expected that centralized portals like “Your Europe” and “Servicesuche Bund” will rarely appear in the top ten search results, as they operate above the local level.

4. Value

This study will help assess how effectively local governments address users’ information needs online. The results can inform digital strategy improvements not only in Germany, but also in other countries aiming to modernize public service delivery. Future research could expand the approach to include longitudinal data or cross-national comparisons.

5. References

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